

ETYMOLOGY OF THE FORMATION OF THE PHYTONOMICS VOCABULARY OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

Khoshimkhujaeva M.M.

PhD TerSU

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6802050>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 28th June 2022

Accepted: 01st July 2022

Online: 06th July 2022

KEY WORDS

phytonim, formation history, historical, social and geographical factors, borrowings.

The study of phytonyms of any language is not possible without taking into account their historical features, i.e. genesis, origin and formation.

Initially, the names of plants, given to distinguish them, appeared spontaneously, like any other lexemes. Later, some names-phytonyms, established in one or another language, turned into terms. But at the same time, a considerable number of words denoting the realities of the plant world passed into the passive stock (ceased to be used in the language, giving way to lexical neologisms). In this respect the phytonymic vocabulary of the English language is quite remarkable.

R.C.A. Prior, in his book on the common names of plants in Britain, writes that English "...fruits, forest trees, cereals, many herbs and medicinal plants today have the same names that have not changed for thousands of years. But a much larger group of plants of other species have names that have been given to them within the last 300 years. Most plant names are

ABSTRACT

This article discusses formation history of phytonymic vocabulary of the English language, examines the historical, social and geographical factors of enrichment and development of modern English plant names.

borrowed by the English language from the languages of other nations - the Romans, the Anglo-Saxons and the Normans who conquered England.

The oldest English phytonyms are phytonyms of Celtic origin. But as a result of various historical events the Celtic language has lost its meaning, so the phytonyms of Celtic characteristic, in the modern English are quite rare. Such is, for example, the phytonym maple, which is part of the vocabulary of modern English literary language: maple is from Anglo-Saxon *mapel-treow* "maple tree", from the ancient Breton *mapulle* "maple". R.C.A. Prior associates this phytonym with the Welsh word *mapwl*, meaning "the outgrowth on a maple tree", and states that in Roman times maple outgrowths were used to make dishes. In all likelihood, the origin of the modern phytonym maple is associated with this very object, which was made from this tree [3, 144].

Along with this, the vocabulary of the English language contains a considerable

number of plant names penetrated from Latin, Greek, Anglo-Saxon, Norman, Lower Germanic, Swedish, Danish, Arabic and Persian. But the greater part, of course, are Latin and Greek loanwords, introduced into English mainly by monks, who, when translating religious or medical texts, simply transferred plant names of Latin and Greek origin to English by transliteration. The following phytonyms are noteworthy in this regard:

1) Latin:

plantag - plantain

bietoria - bistort

2) Greek: κολίανδρο - coriander

ασφόδελος - yellow daffodil

3) translations are calques from Greek:

κοραλλόριζα - coralroot;

This is because Britain was a colony of the Roman Empire before the arrival of the Germans, particularly the Anglo-Saxons, and, like all Roman colonies, it was Christianized until the early fifth century. After the end of Roman rule, Britain was settled by Germanic tribes.

The number of Anglo-Saxon plant names far exceeds the number of Celtic names. These are such lexemes as:

elder - from Anglo-Saxon *ellen*, *ellarn*, meaning "kindler". The word goes back to an earlier Anglo-Saxon word *celd* (from *celan*), associated with the verb *kindle* "to kindle" [3, 71].

elder - goes back to the Proto-Indo-European root *el-*, meaning "red, brown". It has many other derivatives: *elm*, *alder*, *elk*, *auk*, *hellebore*, and *eland* [4].

Some Anglo-Saxon phytonyms are Germanic in origin. Most of them are names of trees widespread in northern Asia: *boak*, *beech*, *birch*, *hawthorn* and *sloe*.

In this respect the history of the Middle English phytonym *æppel* (apple - "any kind of fruit with a spherical shape"), from Proto-Germanic *aplaz* "apple" (cf. Scots. *aipple*, West Frisian *apel*, Dutch *appel*, German *apfel*, Swedish *äpple*), from Proto-Indo-European *h₂éb₁*, *h₂ebōl* (compare Irish *úll*, Lithuanian *óbuolys*, Russian *яблоко*, probably from Greek *ἄμπελος* *ámpelos* "wine") [8].

The connection with other Germanic peoples and their languages is also evident in other phytonyms contained in the phytonymic layer of English. Many of the phytonyms used in the folk lexicon of northern England are of Swedish, Danish or lower Germanic origin. But some of them have become commonly used:

rowan-tree - from Danish *rönn*, from Swedish *runn*, which goes back to the ancient Scandinavian *runa* "talisman"; it is connected with the superstition that rowan protects from the evil eye [3, 198];

buckwheat - from Lower German-Dutch *boekweit* "beech nut", from the resemblance of its triangular seeds to beech nuts [3, 31];

The English vocabulary contains many phytonyms that have penetrated from the French language:

dandelion from the French *dent de lion*, "lion's tooth". It is assumed that 1) the name is associated with the whiteness of the root of the plant; 2) the bright yellow hue of the flower is associated with the heraldic lion, which has teeth of gold; 3) the plant is so named because of the toothed forms of the leaves, which somewhat resemble a lion's jaw [8];

mushroom from the Anglo-French *musherun* from the Old French *meisseron*, appeared in the middle of the XV century in the form of *muscheron*, *musseroun*, the

origin is unclear. Probably derived from the French moss and translated as “something growing in moss” [8];

During the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries, in connection with the territorial expansion of the British Empire and the conquest of more and more land in different parts of the globe, the scope of botanical diversity with which English people were acquainted also expanded. A considerable number of exotic phytonyms were borrowed from:

1) Hindi:

mango - recorded since 1580, from Portuguese manga, which is derived from Malay mangga, taken from Tamil mankay “fruit of the mango tree” (Tamil, India) [8];

2) Australian Aboriginal language (Nyunga):

marri - “eucalyptus aussie”.

Although English was forcibly planted in colonial and semi-colonial countries (India, North America, Australia, New Zealand, South Africa, etc.), nevertheless it could not but absorb into its vocabulary many words from the languages with which it was in contact. Thus, “with the Spanish colonizers in America a number of names entered the phytonomic vocabulary of the English language, which eventually have Mexican, Peruvian, Indian, Brazilian, Haitian origins” [1, 46]. Consequently, many plant names penetrated into English through Spanish:

chilli pepper - from Aztec chili “red chilli pepper” [8];

guava - “guava” from Spanish guaya, from guayaba in the Arawakan language in South America [8];

Undoubtedly, borrowing phytonyms significantly enriched the botanical layer of the English vocabulary, but there is another important factor of enriching the language with new phytonyms. This is a peculiar

mentality and way of life of the English. The English are not only “tireless sailors and explorers, they are also passionate gardeners” [2]. It is not without reason that V. Ovchinnikov in his book “Sakura branch. Oak Roots. Hot Ashes” calls England a country of well-kept green meadows. He writes that “having become the home of the Industrial Revolution, the center of the largest colonial empire, the once agricultural country was spared the need to produce its daily bread. It could afford to be beautiful, and indeed became what we are accustomed to call an English park, that is, a sanctuary not of pristine but of a moderately ennobled nature by man” [2]. In other words, as colonizers and with a great passion for horticulture and floriculture, the English were able to greatly increase the diversity of botanical species at the expense of many exotic plants. But the most important thing here is that it was not simply a process of borrowing names of exotic plants, it was a name designing process in English, as many exotic plants were given English names based on different motivational features. For example:

dicentre is a plant native to Japan, introduced to England in 1840, called keman-sō in Japanese, but in English it has been called bleeding heart or lady-in-a-bath because of the shape of its flowers [7]; brugmansia, a plant native to South America, has various local names such as maikoa, huanduc, maikiua, but in English it is called angel trumpet because of the shape of the flower [5];

pineapple - was originally used to describe the cones of coniferous trees. The term pineapple was first used for this fruit in 1664, when European explorers discovered that this tropical fruit from North and

South America bore a resemblance to conifer cones [6].

Indeed, the English phytonymic vocabulary contains a large number of foreign loanwords or their English forms. The most

important languages which have influenced the formation of the modern phytonymic layer of English are French and Spanish, through which a considerable number of plant names have been borrowed.

References:

1. Берестнева А. В. Названия экзотических растений в английском и русском языках (структурно-словообразовательный и номинативно-мотивационный аспекты). Дис ... канд. филол. наук. – М., 2008. с 25.
2. Овчинников В. Ветка сакуры, Корни дуба, Горячий пепел. – М., 1987.
3. Prior R.C.A. (Приор Р.Ч.А.) On The Popular Names Of British Plants. – London, 1879. 294 pp.
4. [<http://english.stackexchange.com/questions/67718/origin-of-the-word-elder>]
5. [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Brugmansia_suaveolens#cite_note-2]
6. [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pineapple#cite_note-9].
7. [<http://www.cottagesmallholder.com/dicentra-ladies-in-the-bath-bleeding-heart-302/>]
8. [OED - https://www.lexilogos.com/english/english_old.htm]